

Organizational Traps and Public

Bureaucracy:

A Fictional Merger between TVA and StarFleet

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1. Introduction

The literature dedicated to understanding organizational culture is quite broad, and Schein (1986) conceptualizes organizational culture as a set of shared basic assumptions that evolve over time, helping organizations adapt to internal and external challenges. A crucial point in this concept is that the norms and values of an organizational culture need to be shared; in other words, there is no culture in an individual and isolated perspective.

In another seminal work, Hatch (1993) adds symbols and interactive processes to the perspective inaugurated by Schein in the context of organizational culture, by analyzing organizational culture not only in the context of organizations, but also including references from anthropology, sociology, and management.

In the same vein, the literature is also abundant on the study of organizational traps, and there are several traps that can harm the results and efficiency of an organization, from communication problems, especially when senior management does not communicate identified problems clearly and directly, simply seeking to avoid conflicts, promoting superficial harmony that does not solve structural problems, and which can become traps that prevent the organization from developing (Argyris 1986).

In this paper, we argue that cultural misalignment can represent an organizational trap in the context of public agencies' mergers, especially in bureaucratic organizations like the Time Variance Authority (TVA). It is also argued that a merger process between public agencies should be preceded by a due diligence to verify deeply ingrained cultural values and operational paradigms; otherwise, when cultural misalignment takes place, resistance to change will make room, which might, ultimately, erode public values such as equity, adaptability, and trust. A fictional case is used to present a merger between TVA and Starfleet, a more agile, mission-oriented agency, and we use it to analyze and expose how TVA's red tape culture, when left

unexamined, suppresses innovation, erodes public values, and contributes to systemic dysfunction.

Bozeman (1993) presents the red tape theory as a key idea focusing on the organizational traps in the public sector. The author examines the origins of bureaucratic excess in the area and describes how a surfeit of regulation can erect barriers to organizational performance and promote resistance to change, and to other negative outcomes.

When we think of resistance to change in the organizational context, such resistance is linked to both the individual and the system that prevents the implementation of changes, new strategies, new processes or behaviors (Vann 2004).

Kotter (2007) notes that resistance to change is associated with fear of the unknown, complacency, attachment to existing power structures, and dependence on anachronistic organizational norms and systems. The author argues that resistance to change occurs when employees or leaders fail to recognize the urgency and need for change, undermine the implementation of new initiatives, or are otherwise discouraged by the lack of rapid success in implementing measures.

In the current scenario of public administration, the context of mergers between agencies is usually explained based on government efficiency, fiscal responsibility, and the improvement of the administrative process in a broader way. However, when we look beyond the managerial approach that usually explains mergers, we perceive a deeper tension, a tension that questions how public organizations reconcile antagonistic cultural identities, deep-rooted cultural values, and the human factors that influence structural changes.

Schein (1986) argues that organizational culture is not merely a set of norms and procedures, culture represents exactly the set of beliefs that are shared by the people who make up the organization, and that, therefore, shape the behavior of that organization. When these cultural characteristics are not observed in a merger process, or such a situation is simply ignored, the consequences are usually destabilizing for the new organization.

In this article, as stated before, we present a fictional case that explores how agency culture clashes, pitfalls, and resistance to change play important roles in disrupting the smooth flow of an organization's merger, especially when such organizational changes are implemented without regard for the organizations' institutional memory, employee voice, or even democratic accountability.

Using theoretical premises from disciplines such as organizational behavior, public administration, and sociology, we examine a hypothetical merger between two distinct agencies, one rooted in a bureaucratic tradition (Time Variance Agency – TVA), and another agency driven by innovation and mission alignment (Starfleet). It is important to clarify that although the case is fictional for the purpose of achieving greater analogical clarity, the case mirrors real-world situations and illustrates broader systemic challenges.

Beyond the simple analysis of internal dysfunction in such processes, we argue that cultural misalignment and the lack of recognition of resistance to change in merger processes represent a

failure of public values, in this case perceived as an exaggerated preference for efficiency over principles such as equity, adaptability and public trust.

It is not new that mergers between agencies constitute a form of organizational change that affects all levels of the organizations involved, from the individual to the systemic level, and that presents several complexities in its course, significantly altering the dynamics of the organizations involved (Almada, Guimarães & Marques 2018).

This paper seeks to situate such dynamics in a broader context of public administration theory and practice, especially by highlighting implications for ethical leadership, employee well-being and the delivery of responsive governance.

The following sections will present a theoretical review of key constructs, an illustrative case study and a critical discussion of the implications of cultural misalignment in changes such as mergers in the public sector. Our main argument is that mergers that follow the pattern of top-down orders, without due consideration of differences in values and cultures, are doomed not only to operational failure, but also to ethical problems, organizational misbehavior and the erosion of public trust in the long term (Gül & Karabulut 2014). To understand how such cultural tensions manifest, we first examine the distinct organizational cultures of the merging agencies.

2. Different Organizational Cultures: Hypotheses in a Pre-Merger Moment between Public Agencies

In order to present the case that is the object of this work, we will use hypothetical situations, considering fictitious agencies; however, the elements that make up this piece are widely present in the respective literature.

Fiction is a tool that can aid the cognitive process, useful for making sense of a wide variety of situations, allowing for the creation of analogies. In this sense, Weick (1995) argues that fiction offers rich material for constructing meanings, testing assumptions, and also revealing how a wide range of organizational actors interpret ambiguous events. The author states that stories, including fictional ones, are tools that allow us to make sense of events and help us simplify complex and dynamic environments.

Researchers such as Czarniawska (1997) argue that organizations can be studied and understood through a collection of stories, whether real or based on fiction. Regarding fiction, the author argues that fiction allows researchers to go beyond the limits of reality and examine deeper organizational structures, power dynamics, or organizational culture, which are elements that are more difficult to observe directly. Boje (2017) states that much of organizational behavior is influenced and determined by the narratives people use to make sense of their roles, events, and identities. Thus, the use of fictional organizations allows us to make assumptions about the cultural conflicts of different systems, fostering a narrative that makes sense for the purpose of this study.

Fiction and myths provide an emotive and symbolic avenue that allows for the exploration of organizational tensions, and this possibility is extremely useful for analyzing events such as

resistance to change, power flows, and the construction of meaning in the context of bureaucracies (Gabriel, 2000).

In the educational context of public administration, Sementelli and Abel (2007) argue that popular images originating from popular culture, when analyzing the 1980s film *Robocop*, produce useful insights for the field. Goodsell (2014) acknowledges that fictional portrayals are responsible for shaping public perceptions of bureaucracy, and that real tensions are often reproduced alongside the stereotypes created. Scholars must engage with such constructs.

Finally, the use of fiction in this case allows us to create antagonistic organizational cultures (TVA = rigid hierarchical bureaucracy; StarFleet = mission-driven hierarchical), as well as being a useful tool for comparing organizational cultures, allowing us, analogically, to utilize techniques such as Cameron and Quinn's OCAI framework, what would be very difficult to perform with empirical data. Considering the extensive literary support that guides this fictional work, we now present the cases of TVA and Starfleet.

2.1. Time Variance Authority (TVA): The Bulwark of Bureaucracy

Bozeman (1993) in the context of the public sector inaugurates the red tape theory as an anchor of organizational traps for the public sector, and the author presents the origins of excessive bureaucracy in the public context, and that this same excess of control can lead to traps that make organizations ineffective, provoke resistance to change, among other effects.

The Time Variance Authority (TVA) is depicted in *Loki*, a Marvel's TV show available on Disney+, and it offers vivid images of a heavy bureaucratic and hierarchical system, some episodes portray what can be understood as bureaucratic inertia, red tape, resistance to change and dehumanization.

At the beginning of the first episode of the series, entitled *Glorious Purpose*, the character Loki when he joined the TVA is directly confronted by its bureaucratic apparatus when asked about his identity, and if the answer was not expected by the agency, Loki was the risk of being immediately disintegrated, following an excerpt from the episode dialogue that portrays the situation:

Episode 1: *Glorious Purpose*

Scene: Loki's bureaucratic intake at the TVA

Approx. timestamp: 00:05:30–00:05:45

Clerk: *“Please confirm to your knowledge that you are not a fully robotic being, were born an organic creature, and do in fact possess what many cultures would call a soul.”*

Loki: *“I am Loki of Asgard. And I am burdened with glorious purpose.”*

The scene in comment portrays the bureaucratic root of the TVA, highlighting a search for ritualized compliance in its processes, which is directly associated with the concept of Bozeman (1993) of Red Tape, regarding the excess of formalism that is required independently of any rational assessment or logic by the bureaucrat, which is simply required to comply with the rule without worrying whether its application will be created or not.

TVA is a recognized and proven organization with a culture of deep-rooted bureaucracy and hierarchy, and which bases its actions on formal rules, standardized procedures, and detailed regulations. Behavior is practically guided by norms and codes to the detriment of personal judgment and evaluation or flexibility (Diefenbach & Todnem 2012).

TVA is also recognized for having an extremely centralized chain of command, and only those in high management positions are authorized to make decisions, which is where power emanates, while on the other hand, the vast majority occupying lower levels in the organization can decide almost nothing (Diefenbach & Todnem 2012).

The TV show continues to portray the TVA as an extremely hierarchical and averse structure organization to new possibilities, even if they are based on evidence and experiences, denoting the idea of the trap of competence, the use and exploitation of a resource or practice even being inefficient, thus making innovation unfeasible (March 1991). This is the scenario presented in episode 2 of the show, titled *The Variant*, and then transcribed an interesting dialogue that demonstrates the trap of competence subtly and clearly:

Episode 2: *The Variant*

Scene: Mobius and Ravonna discussing Loki's field incursion, which is not in the protocol, and despite Agent Mobius' interesting findings, he was supposed to follow protocol because the Time-Keepers were observing this case closely.

Approx. timestamp: 00:13:30–00:14:45

Mobius: *Listen, Ravonna, I'm sorry. I realize that my, you know, methods with this Loki are controversial, but...*

Ravonna: *Towing a dangerous Variant into the field is controversial.*

Mobius: *Yeah, it didn't go exactly the way I wanted it to today, but here's what we did find out. The Variant likes to stall for time, and, eventually, we'll catch the other one doing the same thing. Because understanding this Loki helps me get closer the one we're chasing. Right?*

Ravonna: *Look, I know you have a soft spot for broken things.*

Mobius: *I don't think so.*

Ravonna: *Yes, you do. But Loki is an evil, lying scourge. That is the part he plays on the Sacred Timeline.*

Mobius: *Maybe he wants to mix it up. Sometimes you get tired of playing the same part. Is that possible? He can change?*

Ravonna: *Not unless the Time-Keepers decree it. And then, it shall be so.*

Mobius: *And how are the old Time-Keepers?*

Ravonna: *(SIGHS) How do you think?*

Mobius: *(CHUCKLES) I don't know. 'Cause I've never met 'em.' Thankfully. Although, I shouldn't say that. The one looks...*

Ravonna: *The Time-Keepers are monitoring every aspect of this case. I've never seen them so involved. They want the Variant caught.*

The clear chains of command reinforce the idea of an organization with rigid, multi-layered structures that define relationships and authority in this organization (Diefenbach & Todnem 2012). Bozeman (1993), in presenting his “red tape” theory, argues that excessive bureaucracy,

as present in the TVA agency, has different sources, from external and internal demands for control, accountability processes, and the fragmentation of political power.

Further on episode 5 of the series, titled Journey to Mystery, is marked by the prune of variants that TVA cannot explain, considering the unfolding of the plot, at that time the TVA agents were pruning the variants without even trying to understand them, or without even investigating the reason for the variants to be, apparently, outside orbit. This behavior reflects a bureaucratic pathology of the TVA, since it did not deal with the complexity that the variants presented, and simply eliminated them. Not dealing with complexities, not adjusting policies when necessary, reveals TVA's resistance to sensemaking, and the agency is intoxicated in its rigid bureaucratic structure, which fatally reverberates as systemic stagnation (Weick 1995).

In this agency, excessive bureaucracy and rigid hierarchy are perceived as a cultural phenomenon, not just a structural issue, and are supported by values such as centralized control, predictability, and preservation of status (Diefenbach & Todnem 2012).

So far, with what has been presented, it is possible to visualize the cultural image of TVA, and in the following section we hypothetically apply the technique for evaluating organizational culture developed by Cameron and Quinn (1999), the Organizational Culture Assessment Instrument (OCAI), a tool capable of presenting a convincing and enlightening visualization of the dominant culture at TVA.

2.1.1 Organizational Culture Assessment Instrument – Case TVA

The Organizational Culture Assessment Instrument is a technique for assessing organizational cultures. It essentially establishes four major types of organizational culture: clan culture, in which the culture adopts a more collaborative, family-like behavior; adhocracy culture, which is fostered by innovative and entrepreneurial behavior; market culture, where competitiveness is ever-present and goal achievement is another constant; and finally, hierarchical culture, where behaviors are rule-based and have more rigid structures (Cameron & Quinn 1999).

Considering cultural types, each organization is assessed across six dimensions, such as leadership style, decision-making process, and organizational glue. Scores are assigned for each of these dimensions, taking into account the four cultural types (Cameron & Quinn 1999). The tool is frequently used in organizations to identify cultural alignment and inform strategies for organizational change.

A fictional diagnosis of the TVA, considering its behavior throughout the show, its policies and organizational logic as portrayed in Loki, would generate the following profile, as depicted in Table 1.

Table 1: Fictional Diagnosis of the TVA

OCAI Dimension	TVA Cultural Type (Score Estimate)
Dominant Characteristics	<i>Hierarchy (9/10)</i>
Leadership Style	<i>Hierarchy (8/10)</i>
Employee Management	<i>Hierarchy (9/10)</i>
Organizational Glue	<i>Policies & Procedures (Hierarchy)</i>

OCAI Dimension	TVA Cultural Type (Score Estimate)
Strategic Emphasis	<i>Predictability & Stability</i>
Criteria for Success	<i>Smooth operations, low deviation</i>

The radar chart presented below gives us better visibility of the predominant cultural type in TVA:

TVA's OCAI Cultural Profile (Fictional Diagnostic)

This assessment clearly demonstrates a cultural profile of the TVA aligned with hierarchy, with minimal characteristics of other cultural types. This cultural trait definitely corroborates its institutional rigidity, which impedes the flexibility necessary for the merger with Starfleet to be successful. On the contrary, as we will discuss later, the TVA's cultural behavior will amplify resistance to change, postpone innovation, and initiate systemic dysfunction (March 1991; Bozeman 1993; Kotter 2007).

2.2. Starfleet Agency: Innovation as a Motto

While TVA represents institutional hierarchical rigidity, appearing as a bastion of bureaucratic organizational culture, Starfleet appears as a counterpoint. Starfleet is a fictional organization in the Star Trek media franchise. It's a complex entity that includes exploration, science, diplomacy, and defense, and its employees are dedicated to all these ideals.

In its command structure, as with TVA, Starfleet is a paramilitary organization, but it is, in fact, very different in terms of cultural focus. The strict Starfleet chain of command has its work shaped by a definite mission and strategic flexibility. Orders are out there somewhere, but are subordinated to a culture that values feedback, decentralized decisions at the tactical level, and rapid adaptation to new environments.

Here, it's precisely the opposite of the TVA's procedural rigidity and hierarchy; order gives way to wildness and disorganization, and no one knows what steps to take. So the conflict between those two organizations, between the TVA and Starfleet, is not really a conflict about having hierarchy so much as it's a conflict about which way it gets applied, how it is interpreted within the culture of the organization.

The main peculiarity of this agency is its mission-oriented culture, which is more flexible and adaptable in relation to rules and regulations. It has some characteristics that reinforce this idea, such as the possibility of individuals aligning their decisions with the organization's main mission, instead of just following orders from superiors or simply complying with regulations; decision-making is decentralized; flexibility and adaptability, since individuals clearly know the organizational mission and are able to react quickly to unexpected situations, among other characteristics (Bolton, Brunnermeier & Veldkamp 2008).

Starfleet is similar to what Bolton et al. (2008) argue about the organizational culture that is based on mission-focused management, as it provides individuals and groups in the organization with greater autonomy, prompt coordination and greater adaptability, provided that individuals are able to internalize this mission clearly, as is the case at Starfleet.

It is also an agency recognized for having an exploratory character, which understands the role of innovation in the continuity and advancement of organizations, as its workforce is more dynamic and open to new ideas and experimentation, understanding that organizational learning embedded in the culture is fundamental to the success of that organization (Mahler 1997).

2.3 Organizational Culture as a Meaning System

Due to a change in government, resulting from the election of a new leader who promised his voters to cut unnecessary government spending at all costs, upon taking office the leader created an agency, called Big Brother, whose objective was to analyze all government spending and its respective agencies.

When analyzing the objectives and functions of the Time Variance Authority and Starfleet agencies, Big Brother understood that there were redundancies in the responsibilities of these agencies, as well as unnecessary spending by the government in maintaining these two agencies, and Big Brother recommended the merger of these two agencies, with a reduction in staff and also in the budget planned for the agencies, which was implemented without any further questions by the central government.

It is also important to note that, unlike what is suggested in the literature, the organizational cultures of the pre-merger agencies were not observed and understood to guide the process of merging the agencies and integration, which would be a determining factor in understanding the possibility of success in the merger process, considering the preponderant role of organizational cultures in such processes (Schraeder & Self 2003).

Another problem with the current merger is that Big Brother failed to take into account that to navigate ambiguities in corporate and organizational environments, people often interpret clues and hints to make sense of situations where there is no clarity, and by ignoring the nebulous

environment created by the merger, leaving people without any basis for making sense of the change they were experiencing, Big Brother failed colossally (Weick 1995).

Then, through an executive order without further details on how the merger should occur, the merger of the agencies was determined, which should occur immediately.

The consolidation of TVA and Starfleet merger represents not only an administrative union but a cultural clash. Whereas Starfleet illustrates a mission-defining adaptability and decentralized learning, TVA represents a profoundly bureaucratic system, with core consumptions of control, hierarchy, and procedural sanction.

These are not just stylistic differences; these are the guiding assumptions that shape how each agency thinks about problems, responds to change, and learns from experience. When such diverse cultures are combined without being consciously aligned, the context is ripe for organizational traps to be developed. These traps, evident in outdated practices, pockets of resistance to new thinking, and patterns of non-adaptation, are not simply individual malfunctions but symptoms of an organization's disregard of culture during its pursuit of change.

In the next section, we discuss how TVA's dominant cultural traits were left unchallenged, allowing competence traps, success traps, and structural inertia to emerge and compromise the success of the merger.

3. Organizational Traps and Learning Failures

To make sense of the unraveling that succeeded the merger between TVA and Starfleet, we need to return to the notion of the organizational trap: the repetitive patterns of behavior and configurations of organizational elements that undermine both learning and responsiveness as well as change (Argyris 1986).

3.1. Competencies as an Organizational Trap Preventing Merger Success

On the one hand, the Starfleet agency was willing to implement the best procedures, seeking cultural convergence with the TVA agency, aiming at the success of the merger process (Bolton et al., 2008), on the other hand, the TVA agency, based on its outdated beliefs and practices, and its rigid and hierarchical structure, prevented any measure from being implemented so that the merger could take place (Liu 2006).

To better illustrate the behavior of the TVA agency, considering that Starfleet had developed a management system software for the agency that was more modern, reliable and much more economical, called DeepSearch, it was suggested that after the merger the agencies should use this new system.

However, this possibility was immediately rejected by the TVA agency, since it was extremely accustomed to using its obsolete system, claiming that the agency's performance ultimately depended on the agency's knowledge of its own system, and that it would not make any sense to change the system since it had been successful in the past (Liu 2006).

This situation can be characterized as a competence trap, since excessive reliance on old practices and customs of the TVA agency can lead to inertia in terms of innovation, and in particular can lead to failure in the post-merger integration process, considering the learning and cultural adaptability of the agencies that are necessary and essential in a merger process (Liu 2006; Gül & Karabulut 2014).

Another practical example that refers to competencies as a trap, preventing the success of the merger process, with regard to the TVA agency, is its inflexibility in relation to the chain of approval of routine tasks, which considerably delays the progress of the integration process, and such behavior reveals that the TVA agency is trapped in its own convictions, routines and mental models, which seem inappropriate for the new environment in which the agency is inserted (Liu 2006).

Finally, the TVA agency refuses through its actions the learning process necessary to go through the merger process, and consequently the exploratory learning process, which seeks innovation and adaptation to the new reality, and the competencies on which the TVA agency is based generate a knowledge gap, which ends up harming and compromising not only the success of the merger integration, but the very existence and continuity of the agencies (March 1991; Gül & Karabulut 2014; Shiri, Bagherzadeh & Ghasempour 2024).

3.2 The Glories of the Past, the Success That Was Left Behind

The two agencies involved in the merger are widely recognized for their past glories, how they managed to achieve success in their missions and gain the trust of the public in general. Regarding the Starfleet agency, considering its more open and innovation-oriented culture, it has always sought to balance the exploitative nature of the skills in practice, and in a balanced way also seeking the exploration of new technologies, techniques and knowledge, aiming at the perpetuation of the agency (March 1991).

On the other hand, the TVA agency in the last years before the merger increasingly clung to its past glories and achievements, believing that nothing would need to change for them to be efficient again, and its employees and leaders reinforced the idea that if in the past it worked and functioned, nothing would need to change, generating complacency and a lack of desire to recognize the necessary adaptation to the change imposed by the merger with the Starfleet agency (Miller 1992; Tushman & O'Reilly 1996).

The mindset rooted in past success and glories at TVA can be understood as an organizational trap, which can lead to the complete failure of the merger integration process with Starfleet, since such a mindset creates greater resistance to the change that is necessary, and such a situation serves as an example of how difficult it is to implement new knowledge and techniques, a challenge that is exacerbated by the inertia caused by past glories (Tushman & O'Reilly 1996).

4. Resistance to change: side effect or desired effect? The manifestation of culture clash and organizational traps

The organizational pathologies that were playing out in the TVA–Starfleet merger, namely the competence trap and the success trap, did not occur in a vacuum. They both strengthened and were strengthened by another potent dynamic: resistance to change.

Such deeply ingrained cultural embedding of routines did not create an environment in which the need for, let alone the acceptance, of some form of adaptation could be seen and accepted by the workforce and leadership alike with respect to the TVA.

As a result, these challenges were both part and parcel of the “trap” and a support to it: Stagnation became a result of and a defense against it. Kotter (2007) and Schein’s (1996) argument that resistance is inevitable in high-control environments such as TVA is supported: when employees identify with existing modes of being or doing, resistance is to be expected. In this section, we take a look at how that resistance played out on either side of the merger, and how, in the end, it unwittingly cemented the very silos that held back integration, innovation, and advancement.

4.1. Resistance at the TVA Agency

As discussed in the introduction to this paper, the concept of resistance to change presented by Kotter (2007), as being the fear of the unknown, complacency, attachment to existing power structures, and dependence on anachronistic organizational norms and systems, presents itself as the perfect model to describe why both individuals and the system resist the change caused by the merger of agencies.

Schein (1996) emphasizes the nature of a deeply rooted culture and how this culture can serve as an obstacle, creating resistance to change that challenges fundamental and basic assumptions, and this is the case of the organizational culture of the TVA agency, deeply rooted in bureaucracy and hierarchical structure.

This same culture is responsible for provoking certain fears in individuals, such as the loss of stability, the lack of predictability regarding the immediate future, and also the establishment of roles, and such fears generate resistance to the merger integration process (Kelman 1958). Individuals perceive the threat posed by the other agency, which is apparently more innovative, potentially more agile in carrying out its tasks and solving problems, and such circumstances act as a natural fuel for the resistance experienced in the process of agency integration (Kelman 1958).

4.2. Resistance at Starfleet Agency

While resistance to change is an expected effect when we culturally analyze the TVA agency, we might think that the opposite would be true for the Starfleet agency. However, this is not the case, as we will analyze below. Lawrence, Lorsch & Garrison (1967) address the difficulties and challenges that exist when it comes to integrating two organizations that have such distinct structures and cultures, as in the case of this work.

As previously presented, the Starfleet agency has a mission-driven, innovative culture, and on the other hand, the agency with which they are merging is known for its excessively bureaucratic

and hierarchical culture, and this situation generates in individuals and leaders a feeling of greater adherence to their previous agency, because they understand that the excessively bureaucratic environment can harm the agency's creativity and autonomy (Appelbaum, Karelis, Le Henaff & McLaughlin 2017).

In addition to the fact that merger processes naturally trigger resistance to change, due to a series of other factors, in the specific case of the Starfleet agency, its individuals perceive that the merger and integration process is a setback for the agency, especially with regard to organizational agility and the organization's mission-driven culture (Appelbaum et al. 2017).

4.3 Resistance as Traps Enablers

At TVA, it is important to highlight that resistance to change in relation to Starfleet's innovative culture was not only rooted in fear of the new but was in many ways reinforced by ingrained bureaucratic structures and routines, whose reward was conformity at all costs and never being willing to experiment; therefore, such resistance produces organizational pitfalls.

It's also important to emphasize that while TVA became entangled in the pitfalls of competition, especially by relying too heavily on outdated technologies and processes, its members increasingly relied on these past practices, resisting the more innovative practices proposed by Starfleet.

While acknowledging that there was resistance from both agencies, it's crucial to clarify that the TVA's resistance was rooted in its own culture, while Starfleet's resistance was based on strategic concerns that the mission would ultimately fail, not simply as a survival strategy.

Table 2 demonstrates in a more playful way the cultural contrast between the agencies in this case, see below.

Table 2: Cultural Contrast between TVA and StarFleet

Cultural Dimension	Time Variance Authority (TVA)	Starfleet Agency
Core Orientation	<i>Rule-based, bureaucratic, control-driven</i>	<i>Mission-oriented, adaptive, innovation-driven</i>
Decision-Making Style	<i>Centralized, hierarchical</i>	<i>Decentralized, collaborative</i>
Communication Norms	<i>Formal, top-down</i>	<i>Open, lateral, and feedback-rich</i>
Learning Style	<i>Exploitative (rely on past success and routines)</i>	<i>Exploratory (experiments, feedback loops, learning-by-doing)</i>
Response to Change	<i>Resistant, slow, requires structural validation</i>	<i>Embraces change, values flexibility</i>
Technology Use	<i>Legacy systems defended on grounds of familiarity</i>	<i>Proactive development and integration of innovative systems (e.g., DeepSearch)</i>

Cultural Dimension	Time Variance Authority (TVA)	Starfleet Agency
View on Authority	<i>Position-based, titles and roles matter most</i>	<i>Competency and mission alignment valued over formal hierarchy</i>
Organizational Identity	<i>Tied to history, institutional reputation, internal protocols</i>	<i>Tied to outcomes, external mission impact, team autonomy</i>
Resistance to Merger	<i>Fear of losing hierarchy and predictability; identity tied to structure</i>	<i>Fear of mission dilution; identity tied to purpose and innovation</i>

The TVA and Starfleet agencies were two fundamentally different organizational culture models, and this agitated post-merger integration difficulties, as indicated by Table 2. These were not only operational differences, but they were ones of value, trust, identity, and ethical coherence.

Finally, considering that March (1991) suggests that organizations that have achieved some degree of success by applying obsolete practices in the past often consider such practices to be absolute truths, this dynamic was clearly demonstrated at TVA, where past success reinforced confidence in the current culture. When minimally challenged by StarFleet's innovative practices and adaptive culture, TVA interpreted this gesture not as an opportunity for change, growth, or innovation, but as a threat to its very existence. It follows that resistance in this case is not merely a defense strategy, but also a strategy for preserving its identity.

5. The Consequence of the Clash of Antagonistic Cultures, Traps and Resistance: Organizational Misbehavior

Merger processes constitute major organizational changes and are among the situations that cause the most stress in employees, especially in the context of the private sector. Regarding the public sector, it is possible to infer that public employees experience the same level of stress, especially when mergers between agencies are determined solely to fulfill political desires and orders, and when they are culturally misaligned (Dorling 2017; Appelbaum et al. 2017). In the fictional case presented here, in the merger between TVA and Starfleet, the tension went beyond administrative limits, as its roots were cultural and existential.

The frustration that is generated in a process of this magnitude cannot be disregarded, especially when we consider the clash of organizational cultures between the TVA and Starfleet agencies, a crucial component to be observed in a merger process that was simply ignored, and which is decisive for the success or complete failure of the merger and integration process between the agencies (Schraeder & Self 2003).

Since there were no previous efforts to build mutual understandings between the agencies, there was no intercultural dialogue, as well as transition strategies between leaderships, fundamental components in a change process of this magnitude, and which, when duly observed, according to the literature, result in successful integrations (Almada, Guimarães, & Marques 2018).

What this means is that if we ignore cultural factors as coordination way will cause more emotional and behavioral problems. In these organizational traps, particularly competence and success traps, the workforce found itself increasingly frustrated, disengaged, and in conflict. When core cultural values are threatened, according to Schein (1996), individuals react defensively since it is necessary to resist imposed change and reinforce old patterns. In this sense, misbehavior is not merely a problem of individual deviancy but should be viewed as symptomatic of system-wide mismanagement of culture and identity.

Unattended cultural conflict and ambiguity can become "petty tyranny," scapegoating, withdrawal, and sabotage (Ashforth 1994). In terms of styles of being in the TVA-Starfleet merger, the types of misbehavior, including a slowdown of work, resistance to cross-functional collaboration and non-utilization of, for instance, new systems, like DeepSearch, manifest themselves as unconscious defense of the threatened organization identity. Robinson and Bennett's (1995) model of deviant workplace behavior provides additional insight by stating that deviance covers a spectrum of behavior extending from petty production (deviance) to more overt counterproductive work behaviors, such as hoarding information and undermining others' efforts.

Additionally, the psychological stress of the merger for employees – what some researchers call “merger syndrome” – may also undermine morale and diminish motivation, a crucial resource for mission-driven agencies (Cartwright and Cooper 1993; Fernandez and Rainey 2006). When people feel their values are being ignored, the decisions are being made without transparency and regard for organizational memory, then it sharply reduces the likelihood that they will contribute to the new social reality we call the institution.

Finally, there are serious inefficiencies when two clashing organizational cultures meet, as TVA and StarFleet did during the integration. It created an emotional climate of hostility, increased opposition to change, and encouraged actions which were to inhibit integration. These results emphasize the importance of culture-centric change management approaches in public sector reforms where the merger objectives are framed solely around efficiency or productivity gains, potentially overlooking the human and cultural aspects of organizational functioning.

6. The Interpretive Framework: Scope and Constraints

We take a conceptual and interpretive approach, employing a form of fictional case analysis to discuss the organizational implications of cultural misfit in public agency mergers. As we're working with fictional groups — most notably here the TVA and Starfleet, respectively — this provides a useful analogical scaffolding to understand what's happening more generally in terms of friction and resistance and the logic of organizations. But there obviously are limits. Because the case is fiction, however, findings are illustrative rather than generalizable, and cultural behaviors represent interpretations of them that are influenced by the narrative style of popular media rather than empirically gathered field data.

A further drawback consists in the lack of qualitative/quantitative evidence generated from “first-hand” reports of real cases of public agencies in the process of fusion. The application of OCAI

to TVA is imaginary and, although beneficial as a diagnostic metaphor, the tool is untested in an actual administrative setting.

Future research may further develop this conceptual base by using instruments such as the OCAI in empirical investigations of public sector mergers or by empirical cross-case studies that examine cultural integration approaches in actual interagency mergers. Relatedly, the potential of fiction and media in public administration pedagogy and theorizing to expose tacit cultural presumptions, power dynamics, and ethical quandaries encountered by public servants require more exploration.

7. Conclusion

As Schein (2010) points out, deeply embedded organizational cultures shape perceptions, values, and behaviors. When merging agencies have different cultures (e.g., a bureaucratic versus an agile culture), inherent differences in operating norms and assumptions can lead to the establishment of competence traps and success traps (Levitt & March 1988; Miller 1990). Reliance on familiar but potentially misaligned competencies or inertia stemming from previous independent successes can impede the adoption of more effective integrated practices.

The experience of being in a competence trap or a success trap can significantly increase resistance to change. Employees in the bureaucratic agency (TVA, in our case) may resist the loss of established routines and hierarchies because their existing competencies, although potentially outdated in the context of the merger, provide comfort and familiarity (Schein 1996). On the other hand, employees in the agile agency (Starfleet) may resist changes that they perceive as leading to increased bureaucracy and stifling innovation, clinging to the successful practices of their pre-merger culture (Burns & Stalker 1994). Kotter (2007) emphasizes that lack of understanding and buy-in, often based on cultural differences and a sense of being trapped in unproductive patterns, is a major factor in resistance.

The ongoing stress and frustration resulting from unresolved cultural conflicts and the sense of being trapped in ineffective patterns can manifest as various forms of organizational misbehavior. As described by Robinson and Bennett (1995), this can range from decreased productivity and absenteeism to more disruptive behaviors such as internal conflicts, sabotage, and even ethical lapses. When employees feel that their cultural values are disregarded, their skills are devalued, and they are forced to work in uncomfortable or seemingly unproductive ways, their commitment and motivation decrease, increasing the likelihood of negative workplace behaviors (Ashforth 1994).

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